

Retheorizing Who Theorizes | Carryall

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18–23 minutes

Joshua L. Crutchfield responds to Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen’s *The Ideas That Made America: A Brief History*.

Getting Beyond Boundaries

Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen’s *The Ideas That Made America* is a brief survey of the “most compelling episodes and abiding preoccupations” that define American intellectual history.^[1] Starting with the first contact between Europeans and Indigenous Americans and ending with our contemporary moment, Ratner-Rosenhagen argues that the movement of ideas has shaped American intellectual history and that these ideas can be tracked across “national borders,” “temporal borders,” and “borders within American culture.”^[2] Ratner-Rosenhagen departs from the foundation that American ideas were never *only* produced in America or confined to it, and this conceptual framework aligns with the growing consensus within the field that suggests that we cannot understand American intellectual history without properly placing it within an international context.

However, perhaps in striving to internationalize US intellectual history, Ratner-Rosenhagen self-admittedly limits the intellectuals from which she mentions mostly to “professional thinkers” and the sources she draws from mostly to “works of philosophy, political and social theory, literature, and cultural criticism.”^[3] As a result, Ratner-Rosenhagen’s survey goes somewhat global, but at the same time it almost exclusively pulls from a European tradition of American thought to define the contours of American intellectual history. New approaches, produced by scholars of African American and African American women’s intellectual history, might help to address this drawback of Ratner-Rosenhagen’s “brief history,” demonstrating how we can expand the very notion of what constitutes knowledge, whom American intellectuals were, the sources they produced, and the discourses in which they engaged. Doing this not only creates a more diverse representation of American intellectual history, but also a far more accurate one.

For a More Inclusive US Intellectual History

African American and African American Women’s intellectual history scholars offer critical insights into how to produce a more inclusive version of American intellectual history through their methodological and theoretical interventions. Due to histories of navigating slavery and Jim Crow, African Americans historically had little to no access to the institutions, professions, or the publishing infrastructure that historians have traditionally relied on to produce intellectual history. While academics have typically privileged written sources, [scholars of African American intellectual history](#) have turned to both traditional and nontraditional written sources and oral traditions to track what African Americans thought about the actions they took.^[4]

Diedra Cooper Owens’ essay “Hapticity and ‘Soul Care’: A Praxis for Understanding

Bondswomen's History" is one recent example of how historians have used nontraditional written sources to elucidate the thoughts of enslaved black women who normally do not get written into the canon of American intellectual history. Owens analyzes the journals of white medical doctors who performed medical procedures and experimentations on enslaved black women. Although sources like medical journals were written by white medical doctors, Owens maintains that the times when black women's voices were included "reveal deep fissures in the ideology of white Southern paternalism and black people's acceptance of this so-called benevolence."^[5] Through her analysis of black women's voices in gynecological medical literature, Owens demonstrates how enslaved women "sparked nineteenth-century discourses on ethics and the moral parameters of womanhood."^[6] The ideas they expressed revealed enslaved black women's *knowledge* about their bodies, pregnancy, and motherhood. Thus, Owens' study shows how enslaved women, like the elite women mentioned in Ratner-Rosenhagen's survey, also participated in the Victorian Era's discourse on womanhood even though they rarely produced their own written sources. By privileging their voices *as knowledge*, Owens also points to how black women's knowledge shaped the burgeoning field of gynecology. Owens' essay skillfully demonstrates that what constitutes knowledge should not be limited to the sources that professional thinkers produced or the discourses to which they contributed.

Owens' scholarship reflects a common theoretical departure point that has emerged among African American and African American Women's intellectual historians: African Americans, even if uneducated, enslaved, or working class, were thinking people who theorized their actions. As Keisha N. Blain, Christopher Cameron, and Ashley D. Farmer contend in [New Perspectives on the Black Intellectual Tradition](#), black folks:

did not simply act on a whim; they carefully thought about their actions, and they carefully devised strategies and tactics. They proposed solutions, they offered critiques, and they challenged others—all the while resisting many of their contemporaries who dismissed their contributions often on account of their education and social standing.^[7]

This basic theory—that people, regardless of their race, gender, or class status, theorize—challenges previous assumptions about what knowledge is, whom intellectuals were, and where across society knowledge production takes place.

Scholars of African American women's intellectual history have further intervened in the field of American intellectual history by broadening the definition of intellectuals. These scholars have included political activists within their formulation of intellectuals who produce critical knowledge. In her article, "[Street Strollers: Grounding the Theory of Black Women Intellectuals](#)," historian Ula Y. Taylor shows how activists Ella Baker and Amy Ashwood Garvey produced knowledge as "street intellectuals" or thinkers who "ground their ideas in the personal, antidotal, and subjective modes." Baker's and Garvey's ideas weren't necessarily produced from formal study, rather they "talk[ed] and [wrote] about what they themselves [were] doing socially and politically."^[8] In contrast to the intellectuals who typically fill the volumes of American intellectual histories, "the life of the street is the primary text for the street strollers."^[9] Scholarship such as Taylor's moves the field of African American intellectual history, never mind the broader one of US intellectual history, past the idea that "men theorized and women organized." It recognizes black women as important theorists who shaped ideas central to African American and American history.^[10]

For example, through her political writings, Ella Baker articulated ideas that centered the experiences and preoccupations of working-class black women. She co-wrote "[The Bronx Slave](#)

[Market](#)” with activists Marvel Cooke, and they published it in the National Association for the Advancement of Colored People’s publication *The Crisis* in November 1935. In the article, Baker and Cooke analyze black women’s experiences obtaining domestic labor in New York City. For a day, the two activists went undercover as domestic laborers who were trying to get a job. The activist pair witnessed domestic laborers waiting on street corners as white women and men inspected and interrogated them to test their fitness to scrub their floors and clean their windows for very little money. This experience, in contrast to formal study, became the basis for articulating the idea that these black women’s experiences resembled the slave block more than “free” labor. For Baker and Cooke, the Bronx Slave Market reflected the broader American political economy and black women’s position at the bottom. “The ‘mart’ is but a miniature mirror of our economic battle front,” they maintained.^[11]

Bronx Slave Market, 1937-1938. Photo: Robert H. McNeill. Source: [Library of Congress](#).

Attention to the political writings of activists such as Baker and Cooper reveal the different preoccupations of black women as organic intellectuals. Baker and Cooke’s comparison of domestic laborers’ experiences obtaining jobs to the slave block advanced the idea that working-class black women experienced “triple-oppression.” Presaging the Combahee River Collective’s observations of “interlocking oppressions” and Kimberlé Crenshaw’s legal concept of “intersectionality,” Baker and Cooke maintained that working-class black women experienced the worst oppression because of their gender, race, and class. They produced these theories based on everyday life experiences that many black women endured and argued that their experiences could be extrapolated out to explain the broader system of American capitalism, racism, and sexism. Other black women such as Claudia Jones and Mae Mallory would later take up and expand on this idea.^[12]

Unlocking Mae Mallory’s Jail Writings

My own research on the political activist Mae Mallory reflects these approaches to African American and African American women’s intellectual history and pushes the field to consider new

sites of black women's knowledge production. Mallory was born into a working-class family in Macon, Georgia on June 9, 1927. She joined the Great Migration and move to New York in 1939. By 1946, Mallory was a divorced mother of 2 children. She worked various odd end jobs in sweat shops and as a domestic laborer to make ends meet. She also utilized welfare services to supplement her income and lived in housing projects to subsidize her housing. At face value, many would not consider Mallory an intellectual, however her experiences navigating poor material conditions as a working-class black woman was the "study" that informed her thinking.^[13] Her jail writings reveal just some of Mallory's contributions toward shaping American intellectual life.

Mallory landed in jail following an incident in Monroe, North Carolina in August 1961. By the mid-1950s, she had become an activist who led and participated in desegregation campaigns in New York and across the country. In 1954, Mallory became the first person to sue a northern school system for de facto segregation. In 1961, she traveled to Monroe, North Carolina to support Robert F. Williams and the Monroe National Association for the Advancement of Colored People's efforts to desegregate their pools. On August 27, 1961, Mallory was involved in an incident in Monroe, where a white couple who was antagonistic to the desegregation protest, accused Mallory of kidnapping them. Following this episode, Mallory fled Monroe and was later caught in Ohio where officials imprisoned her in Cuyahoga County Jail.

Committee to Aid the Monroe Defendants, "The Situation in Monroe, N.C.," ca. 1961.

Mallory believed that her imprisonment was a political frame-up and represented the consequences for black activists who challenged the status quo in America. She expressed her ideas through private and published jail writings. Here is a case of writing, but not in the modes that Ratner-Rosenhagen concentrates on in *The Ideas that Made America*. Mallory's writings joined a black literary tradition of imprisoned literature that blossomed and gained wide-spread popularity during the 1960s and 1970s. Black Power-era imprisoned writers such as Mallory produced letters, essays, newsletters, statements, and poetry, and they innovatively, and many times illegally, circulated these writings within and outside the jail and prison walls.

Activist groups and defense committees published many of these writings to garner financial and moral support from the public. Publishers also aided in the dissemination of imprisoned literature by publishing prison literature where writers used jail and prison cells as sites to critique American oppression. Well before the well-known examples like Eldridge Cleaver's *Soul on Ice*, Jonathan Jackson's *Soledad Brother*, and Angela Y. Davis *If They Come in the Morning*, Mallory's used her jail writings to spread her ideas.^[14] Although Mallory never published a book on political theory or a large volume reflecting on the meaning of America, her writings, nonetheless, demonstrate that she participated in national debates about freedom, self-determination, self-defense, black women's liberation, and the role of carceral institutions within American life that preoccupied the minds of many black Americans during the 1960s and 1970s.

Cuyahoga County Criminal Court Building, Cleveland, OH, ca. 1933. Source: [Library of Congress](#).

One private journal entry Mallory wrote on March 1, 1962, while imprisoned, highlights her critiques about the function of carceral institutions within American society. Mallory frequently wrote descriptions about the women that she was incarcerated alongside to show that most inmates were victims of oppressive conditions rather than themselves perpetrators of crime. In the entry, she discusses a fellow inmate named Callie, who Mallory describes as a “broke” woman with serious health concerns.^[15] The description reflects Callie’s experience navigating poverty and poor medical care, which she had in common with other incarcerated women. Mallory asserts that Callie “rebelled against” these conditions with “a case of robbery.”^[16] Even in these few descriptive phrases, Mallory contributes to emerging American debates about “law and order” during the 1960s and 1970s. They express a viewpoint at odds with the prevailing ethos among conservatives and even liberals moving rightward at the time. Her descriptions flip the legal paradigm, with its historical roots in slave systems and Jim Crow strategies of control through use of flimsy legal strictures, on its head. While the larger society, still dominated by white supremacy, considered Callie’s robbery a crime, Mallory reasoned that she was merely rebelling against her poverty. Imprisoned within a system designed to punish poor African American women, Mallory used descriptions of inmates such as Callie to contextualize black women’s supposed crimes. They needed to be “rethought” within broader structures of oppression, control, and exploitation experienced by black women.

Unexpected Places

Mallory’s thinking and writing highlight how historians of American intellectual history should expand the sites where we search for ideas. Just as scholars of slavery have highlighted the rich world that enslaved people generated despite little formal education produced on plantations, my work has pointed to jails and prisons as critical sites of knowledge for black political activists. When we shift from the courthouse to the jailhouse, we discover radical different perspectives within what is also, in fact, a shared conversation about what is just, right, and fair in a nation’s laws and society.

Historians should continue to look toward nontraditional sites for “ideas” that come from “[unexpected places](#).”^[17] To make such interventions teaches us that historians do not need to rely solely on traditional methodologies, sources, or sites to write intellectual history. In fact, traditional approaches can limit the myriad ways that individuals throughout American history produced knowledge. By utilizing the innovative approaches that scholars of African American and African American women’s intellectual history have developed, we can widen American intellectual

history's reach and significance to people who have not usually been included within the field but have been thinking deeply all along. This will allow us to write a more inclusive and diverse history that also can hear the voices from those who have been marginalized from the field. Race, gender, class, sexuality, and ability distinctions should no longer keep their important ideas locked up.

About the Author

Joshua L. Crutchfield is a writer, historian, and scholar of 20th century black freedom movements, intellectual history and carceral studies. He is a postdoctoral fellow in the Department of Black Studies at Northwestern University where he's working on his book manuscript titled, "Imprisoned Black Women Intellectuals: Mae Mallory, Angela Davis, Assata Shakur, Safiya Bukhari and the Struggle for Abolition, 1955-1983."

Notes

- [1] Jennifer Ratner-Rosenhagen, *The Ideas That Made America: A Brief History* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2019), 1.
- [2] Ratner-Rosenhagen, *The Ideas That Made America*, 4-5.
- [3] Ratner-Rosenhagen, *The Ideas That Made America*, 3.
- [4] Brandon R. Byrd, "The Rise of African American Intellectual History," *Modern Intellectual History* 18, 3 (September 2021): 848.
- [5] Deirdre Cooper Owens, "Hapticity and 'Soul Care': A Praxis for Understanding Bondwomen's History," in *Ideas in Unexpected Places: Reimagining Black Intellectual History*, eds. Brandon R. Byrd, Leslie M. Alexander, and Russell John Rickford (Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press, 2022), 54.
- [6] Cooper Owens, 50.
- [7] Keisha N. Blain, Christopher Cameron, and Ashley D. Farmer, "Introduction," in *New Perspectives on the Black Intellectual Tradition*, eds. Keisha N. Blain, Christopher Cameron, and Ashley Dawn Farmer (Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press, 2018), 4.
- [8] Ula Y. Taylor, "Street Strollers: Grounding the Theory of Black Women Intellectuals," *Afro-Americans in New York Life and History* 30, 2 (July 2006): 154.
- [9] Ula Y. Taylor, 154.
- [10] Ashley D. Farmer, *Remaking Black Power: How Black Women Transformed an Era* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2017), 14.
- [11] Marvel Cooke and Ella Baker, "The Bronx Slave Market," *The Crisis* 42, 11 (1935): 340.
- [12] For example, see Claudia Jones, "An End to the Neglect of the Problems of the Negro Woman!," in *Words of Fire: An Anthology of African-American Feminist Thought*, eds. Beverly Guy-Sheftall and Johnnetta B Cole (New York: The New Press, 1995), 135–51.
- [13] For more information on Mallory, see Paula Marie Seniors, *Mae Mallory, the Monroe Defense Committee, and World Revolutions: African American Women Radical Activists* (Athens: University of Georgia Press, 2024).
- [14] Eldridge Cleaver, *Soul on Ice* (New York: McGraw-Hill, 1967); George Jackson, *Soledad Brother: The Prison Letters of George Jackson* (Chicago: Lawrence Hill Books, 1994); Angela Y. Davis, *If They Come in the Morning: Voices of Resistance* (New York: Third Press, 1971). For

more on prison writings as a genre, see H. Bruce Franklin, *Prison Writing in 20th-Century* (New York: Penguin Books, 1998); Lee Bernstein, *America Is the Prison: Arts and Politics in Prison in the 1970s* (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2010), 99-128. For an international survey of prison writings, see Claire Westall and Michelle Kelly, eds., *Prison Writing and the Literary World: Imprisonment, Institutionalization and Questions of Literary Practice* (New York: Routledge, 2020).

[15] Mae Mallory, Personal Letter, 1 March 1962, Mae Mallory Papers, Box 1, Folder 6, Archives of Labor and Urban Affairs, Wayne State University.

[16] Mae Mallory, Personal Letter.

[17] Byrd, Alexander, and Rickford, eds., *Ideas in Unexpected Places*.

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